

1 **The Derived-Band Envelope Following Response and its Sensi-**
2 **tivity to Sensorineural Hearing Deficits**

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28 **Abstract**

29 The envelope following response (EFR) has been proposed as a non-invasive
30 marker of synaptopathy in animal models. However, its amplitude is affected
31 by the spread of basilar-membrane excitation and other coexisting sensorineu-
32 ral hearing deficits. This study aims to (i) improve frequency specificity of the
33 EFR by introducing a derived-band EFR (DBEFR) technique and (ii) investigate
34 the effect of lifetime noise exposure, age and outer-hair-cell (OHC) damage on
35 DBEFR magnitudes. Additionally, we adopt a modelling approach to validate the
36 frequency-specificity of the DBEFR and test how different aspects of sensorineural
37 hearing loss affect peripheral generators. The combined analysis of simulations
38 and experimental data proposes that the DBEFRs extracted from the [2-6]-kHz
39 frequency band is a sensitive and frequency-specific measure of synaptopathy in hu-
40 mans. Individual variability in DBEFR magnitudes among listeners with normal
41 audiograms was explained by their self-reported amount of experienced lifetime
42 noise-exposure and corresponded to amplitude variability predicted by synaptopa-
43 thy. Older listeners consistently had reduced DBEFR magnitudes in comparison
44 to young normal-hearing listeners, in correspondence to how age-induced synap-
45 topathy affects EFRs and compromises temporal envelope encoding. Lastly, OHC
46 damage was also seen to affect the DBEFR magnitude, hence this marker should be
47 combined with a sensitive marker of OHC-damage to offer a differential diagnosis
48 of synaptopathy in listeners with impaired audiograms.

49 **Keywords**

50 derived-band envelope following response; cochlear synaptopathy; sensorien-
51 ral hearing-loss; supra-threshold hearing deficits

52 1. Introduction

53 Struggling to understand speech in noisy environments is a prevalent complaint
54 of the ageing population, even when they have normal audiometric thresholds.
55 Although hearing thresholds are informative about the sensory function of the
56 cochlea, they are insensitive to auditory-nerve (AN) fiber loss, which is the first
57 sign of permanent hearing damage (Kujawa and Liberman, 2009; Liberman and
58 Kujawa, 2017) and related to supra-threshold hearing (Bharadwaj et al., 2014).
59 Recent animal studies have shown that ageing, ototoxicity and overexposure to
60 noise can lead to an irreversible loss of AN synapses, i.e. cochlear synaptopathy
61 (CS), and delayed degeneration of cochlear neurons, while leaving the cochlear
62 sensory hair cells intact (Kujawa and Liberman, 2009; Lin et al., 2011; Liu et al.,
63 2012; Furman et al., 2013; Lobarinas et al., 2017; Valero et al., 2017). Even
64 when the noise exposure dose only causes a temporary threshold shift (Kujawa
65 and Liberman, 2009), noise-induced AN fibers degeneration can progress through
66 the lifespan and yield an increased sensitivity of the ear to age-induced hearing
67 dysfunction (Fernandez et al., 2015). Additionally, reduced numbers of spiral
68 ganglion cells in post-mortem histology of human temporal bones with preserved
69 sensory cells, confirmed the existence of age-related CS in humans (Makary et al.,
70 2011; Viana et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2019). Thus, noise exposure and ageing are
71 important causes of CS, a deficit which compromises the temporal coding fidelity
72 of supra-threshold sound as a result of a reduced number of afferent AN synapses
73 innervating the inner hair cell (Bharadwaj et al., 2014, 2015).

74 Since the discovery of CS, several attempts have been made to associate changes
75 in indirect and non-invasive measures of auditory function such as scalp-recorded
76 auditory evoked potentials (AEPs) to the histologically quantified degree of AN
77 fibers loss in animals. For example, auditory brainstem responses (ABRs), evoked
78 by transient stimuli and reflecting the synchronized onset responses of AN fibers

79 (Don and Eggermont, 1978) showed a decreased supra-threshold wave-I amplitude
80 after synaptopathy due to noise-exposure (Kujawa and Liberman, 2009; Lobarinas
81 et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2011), despite recovered normal distortion product otoa-
82 coustic emission (DPOAE) and ABR thresholds. The number of AN fibers can
83 also be quantified using envelope following responses (EFRs), which capture how
84 well AN fibers can phase-lock to the stimulus envelope (Joris and Yin, 1992). The
85 EFR can be extracted from scalp-electrodes in response to a sinusoidally ampli-
86 tude modulated (SAM) pure-tone stimulus (Bharadwaj et al., 2014), and has been
87 proposed as an AEP-based measure of CS (Shaheen et al., 2015; Parthasarathy
88 and Kujawa, 2018).

89 Despite the strong relation between AEP markers and CS in animal studies, the
90 indirect nature of AEP recordings hinders a clear and direct interpretation of re-
91 sponse strength in terms of CS. First of all, a mixture of sources contribute to scalp
92 potentials, some of which are electrical activity induced by subject-specific factors
93 and unrelated to the sound-driven response (e.g. head size, age, sex, geometry
94 of the generators and physiological noise level; Trune et al., 1988; Mitchell et al.,
95 1989; Bharadwaj et al., 2014; Plack et al., 2016). Other sources relate to the sound-
96 driven response but depend on outer-hair-cell (OHC) health (Gorga et al., 1985)
97 or cochlear tonotopy (Don and Eggermont, 1978). Lastly, the scalp-recorded AEP
98 is strongly influenced by stimulus characteristics and the corresponding spread
99 of basilar-membrane (BM) excitation, which can confound a frequency-specific
100 diagnosis of CS (Bharadwaj et al., 2014, 2015; Verhulst et al., 2018a; Encina-
101 Llamas et al., 2019). To address these issues, several studies have proposed dif-
102 ferential/relative AEP-based metrics: the EFR amplitude slope as a function of
103 modulation depth (Bharadwaj et al., 2014, 2015; Guest et al., 2018), ABR wave-V
104 latency changes in different levels of background noise (Mehraei et al., 2016), or the
105 combined use of noise-floor corrected EFRs with ABRs to segregate mixed hear-

106 ing pathologies and normalize inter-individual variabilities (Vasilkov and Verhulst,
107 2019, preprint). Secondly, a number of techniques have been proposed to confine
108 ABR generation to specific frequency bands: the use of simultaneous off-frequency
109 masking paradigms, i.e. the derived-band ABR (Eggermont, 1976; Don and Eg-
110 germont, 1978), tone-burst ABRs (Rasetshwane et al., 2013) and notched noise
111 paradigms (Abdala and Folsom, 1995). Lastly, asynchrony of low-spontaneous
112 rate (LSR) AN fibers to the transient stimulus (Bourien et al., 2014) may limit
113 the use of the ABR wave-I amplitude to capture all aspects of CS, as noise-induced
114 CS might preferentially affect LSR AN fibers (Furman et al., 2013).

115 This study proposes the use of a relative derived-band EFR method (DBEFR),
116 to confine the EFR to a specific frequency band. To construct DBEFRs, we
117 changed the bandwidth of the stimulus on the low-frequency side rather than
118 using off-frequency masking methods. Thus, a consecutive subtraction of re-
119 sponses to stimuli with various bandwidths will yield a relative measure of supra-
120 threshold sound coding. We further hypothesize that the relative metric design
121 of the DBEFR reduces the impact of subject-specific factors and increases its
122 sensitivity to individual sensorineural hearing deficits. DBEFR magnitudes were
123 extracted from individuals in four groups to study their applicability to diagnose
124 sensorineural hearing deficits: (1) a young normal-hearing control group, (2) a
125 group with self-reported hearing difficulties in noisy environments, (3) a group
126 of older listeners with normal audiograms and (4) an age-matched group with
127 sloping high-frequency audiograms. We assumed that the second group might be
128 affected by CS due to noise overexposure or ageing and that the third group might
129 be affected by age-induced CS, without co-occurring OHC damage. Aside from
130 collecting DBEFRs, we assessed individual OHC function using audiometric and
131 DPOAE thresholds. In line with animal studies of age-related and noise-induced
132 synaptopathy, we expect that the DBEFR will be reduced in all but the control

133 group.

134 Because, a direct assessment of the individual degree of OHC and AN damage
135 is presently experimentally impossible, we complemented our experimental work
136 with a modelling approach to better understand the relationship between sen-
137 sorineural pathologies and their effect on the peripheral generators of the DBEFR.
138 Models can study how AN fiber and sensory hair cell damage impacts the EFR
139 generators to understand their respective roles for DBEFR generation (Verhulst
140 et al., 2016, 2018a,b). We adopt a biophysically inspired model of the human au-
141 ditory periphery calibrated for ABR and EFR simulation (Verhulst et al., 2018a)
142 and considered the simulations together with the data to interpret the implications
143 of our findings for DBEFR-based hearing diagnostics.

144 **2. Materials and Methods**

145 Two experiments were conducted at two recording locations. In the first exper-
146 iment (Ghent University), normal-hearing (NH) and listeners with self-reported
147 hearing difficulties (NHSR) participated. In the second experiment (Oldenburg
148 University), a total of 43 participants were recruited in three groups: a young NH
149 control group (yNH), an older NH group (oNH) and an older group with sloping
150 high-frequency audiogram (oHI). Ethical approvals were obtained from Ghent and
151 Oldenburg Universities and all participants were informed about the experimental
152 procedures and signed an informed consent before the experiment.

153 *2.1. Participants*

154 16 NH listeners with ages between 18 and 30 (NH: 24.21 ± 4.10 years, five
155 females) and 9 NH subjects with self-reported hearing difficulties (NHSR) with
156 ages between 23 to 49 (NHSR: 33.78 ± 8.57 years, three females) participated in
157 the first experiment. The NHSR participants were recruited using a flyer asking

158 whether they had speech understanding difficulties in the presence of background
159 noise, while not presently being treated for hearing disorders. Measurements were
160 conducted in two sessions per subject, with a maximum sound exposure time of 90
161 minutes per session. The participants filled out a questionnaire, in which they were
162 asked how often (yearly, monthly, weekly or daily) they had been playing a musical
163 instrument in a band, attended festivals, concerts or discotheques and used noisy
164 tools during their lifetime. Moreover, the total number of noise-exposed sessions,
165 their duration and estimated noise loudness (a score between 1 to 5) were also
166 assessed (Degeest et al., 2014). Audiograms were measured with an Interacoustics
167 Clinical Computer Audiometer (AC5) at ten standard frequencies between 0.25
168 and 8 kHz.

169 The second experiment was conducted with three participant groups composed
170 of: 15 young normal-hearing (yNH: 24.53 ± 2.26 years, eight female), 16 old normal-
171 hearing (oNH: 64.25 ± 1.88 years, eight female) and 12 old hearing-impaired (oHI:
172 65.33 ± 1.87 years, seven female) participants. All yNH participants had pure-
173 tone thresholds below 20 dB-HL at all measured frequencies between 0.125 and
174 10 kHz (Auritec AT900, Hamburg, Germany audiometer). In both experiments,
175 the audiometrically better ear was chosen for the experiment and stimuli were
176 presented monaurally while participants were seated in a comfortable chair in an
177 acoustically and electrically shielded sound booth, watching silent movies with
178 subtitles to stay awake. Figure 1 shows audiograms of the subjects in all groups.
179 From here on, \triangle stands for the NH group in the first experiment, \square for NHR
180 group, \diamond for yNH in the second experiment, \circ for oNH and \triangleleft for oHI group.

181 2.2. Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emissions (DPOAEs)

182 In the first experiment, DPOAEs were recorded to ten primary-level pairs, (L_1 ,
183 L_2), at nine primary-frequency pairs: $f_2 = [546, 780, 1002, 1476, 1998, 3012, 3996,$

184 6006, 8003] and $f_1 = f_2/1.2$. L_2 ranged from 20 to 65 dB-SPL in 5 dB steps and L_1
185 $= 0.4L_2 + 39$ dB, according to the scissors paradigm (Kummer et al., 1998). The
186 nine primary frequency pairs were chosen to have complete stimulus periods of the
187 primaries in each pair. For each frequency and level pair, 45 repetitions were gener-
188 ated in MATLAB 2016b and an ER-10X extended-bandwidth Etymotic Research
189 probe system was used to deliver the two pure tones via a loudspeaker/microphone
190 probe inserted in the ear-canal using a silicone eartip. The response was recorded
191 and digitized using a Fireface UCX external sound card (RME). The pure tones
192 were calibrated separately using a B&K artificial ear and B&K sound level meter
193 at each primary frequency, separately. The time-domain ear-canal recordings were
194 converted to pressure using the microphone sensitivity ($50 \frac{mV}{Pa}$) and pre-amplifier
195 gain (40 dB). Then, I/O functions were calculated for the measured primary-
196 frequency pairs by defining the L_{DP} as the averaged spectrum magnitude at the
197 $2f_1-f_2$ cubic distortion frequency, multiplied by $\frac{2}{N\sqrt{2}}$, where N is the number of
198 samples at each f_2 response. Finally, a linear function, i.e. $L_{DP} = aL_2 + b$, was fit
199 to the bootstrapped data-points and the crossing point with $L_{DP}=0$ Pa was defined
200 as the DPOAE threshold at the measured f_2 frequency. DPOAEs in the second ex-
201 periment were acquired using a custom-made software (Mauermann, 2013) which
202 implements a primary frequency sweep method at a fixed f_2/f_1 of 1.2 (Long et al.,
203 2008). The primary frequencies were swept across an 1/3 octave range around the
204 $f_2 = 4$ kHz geometric mean with a duration of 2s/octave. Primary levels were cho-
205 sen according to the scissors paradigm (Kummer et al., 1998). DPOAE threshold
206 at each frequency was calculated by fitting a linear function to the bootstrapped
207 data-points and was extrapolated to cross $L_{DP}=0$ Pa. Additional details on the
208 experimental procedure can be found in Verhulst et al. (2016).

209 *2.3. Envelope Following Responses (EFRs)*

210 The EFR stimuli in the first experiment were five filtered white noise carriers,
211 which were 100% modulated with a 120-Hz sinusoid. To generate them, the white
212 noise was filtered between the following frequency regions: [0.25-22], [0.5-22], [1-
213 22], [2-22] and [4-22] kHz, using a 1024th order FIR band-pass filter designed by
214 the Blackman-window method. In each frequency band, a stimulus with a duration
215 of 1.25 s was generated in MATLAB 2016b, windowed with a 1.25% cosine-tapered
216 window and delivered monaurally over ER-2 earphones, connected to a Fireface
217 UCX external sound card (RME) and a TDT-HB7 headphone driver. A uniformly-
218 distributed random silence jitter was applied between consecutive epochs (200
219 ms \pm 20 ms) of the 370 stimulus presentations. Stimuli with various bandwidths
220 were calibrated to have the same spectral magnitude, i.e. the widest bandwidth
221 stimulus was presented at 70-dB-SPL, while narrower bandwidth stimuli had lower
222 sound pressure levels to preserve an equal spectral level in all conditions. The
223 calibration was performed using a B&K sound-level-meter type 2606. Figure 2a
224 illustrates the designed stimuli in the frequency domain. Scalp-recorded potentials
225 were obtained with a 64-Channel Biosemi EEG recording system and a custom-
226 built trigger box using a sampling frequency of 16384 Hz. The electrodes were
227 placed according to the 10-20 standard, using highly conductive gel (Signa gel).
228 The Common Mode Sense (CMD) and Driven Right Leg (DRL) electrodes were
229 placed on top of the head. Six external channels were used as well, i.e. two
230 earlobe electrodes as reference and the remaining electrodes were placed on the
231 forehead and cheeks to record electrical activity induced by horizontal and vertical
232 eye movements. All channels were re-referenced to the average of the two earlobe
233 electrodes.

234 In the second experiment, four EFR stimuli with white noise carriers were
235 band-pass filtered using the same filter as in the first experiment in [0.3-16], [0.7-

236 16], [2.8-16] and [5.6-16] kHz frequency regions. The precise lower cut-off fre-
237 quencies employed in the band-pass filtering were $\frac{0.5}{\sqrt{2}}$, $0.5\sqrt{2}$, $\frac{4}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $4\sqrt{2}$ kHz,
238 respectively. Stimuli were 95% modulated with a 120-Hz pure tone and presented
239 at 70 dB SPL using the same configuration as the first experiment. The stimuli
240 had a duration of 400 ms, were 2.5% ramped with a tapered-cosine window and
241 presented 1000 times using a uniformly distributed random inter-stimulus silence
242 jitter of $100 \text{ ms} \pm 10 \text{ ms}$. The calibration was performed in the same way as for
243 the first experiment, but using B&K sound level meter type 2610. A 64-channel
244 Biosemi EEG system was adopted to record the responses using EEG caps with
245 equidistant electrode spacing. The CMS and DRL electrodes were located on the
246 fronto-central midline and on the tip of the nose of the participants, respectively.

247 **3. EFR Analysis**

248 Acquired EFRs were first filtered using an 800th order Blackman window-based
249 FIR filter between 60 and 600 Hz, using the *filtfilt* function of MATLAB to avoid
250 time delays and phase shifts. Signals were broken into 1-s long epochs relative to
251 the trigger onset, from 0.25 to 1.25 s in the first and into 0.3-s long epochs, from
252 0.1 to 0.4 s in the second experiment. Baseline correction was applied before the
253 epochs were averaged across trials. 30 and 100 epochs were rejected on the basis of
254 the highest peak-to-trough values in the first and second experiment, respectively.
255 Since the firing patterns of neurons are influenced by factors such as instantaneous
256 external inputs, previous firing patterns and the general state of the system, the
257 interpretation of the raw EFR spectrum resulting from the Fast Fourier Transform
258 (FFT) of the averaged epochs is challenging. Synaptic delays and axon conduc-
259 tion limitations cause a $\frac{1}{f}$ behaviour in EEG (Buzsaki, 2006, Chapter 10) and it is
260 crucial to suppress this noise-floor to analyse the stimulus-driven spectrum. The
261 bootstrapping approach proposed in Zhu et al. (2013) was employed to estimate

262 the $\frac{1}{T}$ noise-floor component. First, 340 epochs were drawn randomly with re-
 263 placement, among the 340 epochs (900 epochs in the second experiment). Then,
 264 the FFT of these epochs were averaged. This procedure was repeated $N_1=200$
 265 times ($N_2=400$ for the second experiment), resulting in a nearly Gaussian dis-
 266 tribution of raw, averaged spectra. The average value of this distribution yielded
 267 the frequency domain representation of the EFRs. Afterwards, the same procedure
 268 with $M_1=1000$ repetitions ($M_2=1200$ for the second experiment) and phase-flipped
 269 (180°) odd epochs was followed to estimate the spectral noise-floor as a function
 270 of frequency. The idea behind this approach is that the time-locked response is
 271 suppressed if the averaging is repeated sufficiently across phase-inverted epochs.
 272 Finally, the averaged absolute values of the estimated noise floors were subtracted
 273 from the averaged absolute values of the EFR spectra amplitudes to obtain the
 274 stimulus-driven EFR spectrum:

$$\text{EFR}_{\text{raw}}(f) = \frac{2}{n_p} \left| \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{FFT}(X_i)}{N_p} \right| \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Noisefloor}(f) = \frac{2}{n_p} \left| \frac{\sum_{j=1}^M \text{FFT}([-1]^j X_j)}{M_p} \right| \quad (2)$$

$$\text{EFR}_{\text{Spec}}(f) = \text{EFR}_{\text{raw}}(f) - \text{Noisefloor}(f) \quad (3)$$

275
 276 X represents the epochs vector, N the number of bootstrap repetitions, M the num-
 277 ber of repetitions to estimate the noise-floor, p the experiment number (i.e. one or
 278 two) and n equals the number of FFT points ($n_1=16384$ and $n_2=8192$). Figure 3
 279 represents EFR_{raw} , Noisefloor and EFR_{Spec} spectra of subject No. 8 from NH
 280 group in the first experiment. All EFR_{Spec} peak values which were four standard

281 deviations above the noise-floor ($\text{EFR}_{\text{SpecSD}}$) for frequencies corresponding to the
 282 modulation frequency (120 Hz) and its following two harmonics (240 and 360 Hz)
 283 were added to yield EFR magnitude of the corresponding condition.

$$\text{EFR}_{\text{PtN}} = \sum_{k=0}^2 \text{EFR}_{\text{SpecSD}}(f_k), \quad f_k = 120 \times (k + 1) \quad (4)$$

284 To construct DBEFRs, the calculated EFR_{PtN} for each narrower-band condi-
 285 tion was subtracted from the following wider-band condition using:

$$\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}} = \begin{cases} (\text{EFR}_{\text{PtN}})_{\text{wide}} - (\text{EFR}_{\text{PtN}})_{\text{narrow}}, & (\text{EFR}_{\text{PtN}})_{\text{wide}} > (\text{EFR}_{\text{PtN}})_{\text{narrow}} \\ 0, & (\text{EFR}_{\text{PtN}})_{\text{wide}} \leq (\text{EFR}_{\text{PtN}})_{\text{narrow}} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

286 Derived frequency bands from EFRs to the first experimental stimuli are shown
 287 schematically in Fig. 2b.

288 4. Questionnaire analysis

289 The completed questionnaires from the participants in the first experiment
 290 were used to estimate the individual life-time noise exposure dose. To this end, the
 291 collected individual data related to the frequency and duration of experienced noise
 292 exposure were converted to a number of sessions per year multiplied by the duration
 293 and the personal estimated noise loudness scores, i.e. a number between 1 and 5.
 294 We followed the procedures as described in Degeest et al. (2014). The scores were
 295 separately calculated for questionnaire categories: (i) playing musical instrument
 296 in a band, (ii) attending festivals, concerts and discotheques and (iii) using noisy
 297 tools. Outcomes were normalized across NH and NHSR groups participants by
 298 the highest reported dose, i.e. 30600, 18480 and 26000 hours in each category,

299 respectively.

300 5. Model Simulations

301 A biophysical model of the human auditory periphery (Verhulst et al., 2018a),
302 schematically shown in Fig. 4, was adopted to simulate the experimental con-
303 ditions and to investigate the effect of different aspects of sensorineural hearing
304 deficits on the EFR_{PtN} and $DBEFR_{PtN}$ magnitudes. The original implementation
305 of the model is described in Verhulst et al. (2018a) and can be downloaded from
306 “<https://github.com/HearingTechnology/Verhulstetal2018Model>”. The parameters
307 which determine the weights between the population AN, cochlear nucleus (CN)
308 and inferior colliculus (IC) responses were adjusted along with the AN innervation
309 patterns across CF for the purpose of this study.

310 5.1. Auditory nerve-fiber distribution

311 The original model implementation introduced the same number of synapses
312 between inner-hair-cells (IHCs) and AN fibers for all simulated characteristic fre-
313 quencies (CF), whereas human and rhesus monkey innervation patterns show a
314 bell-shaped pattern across CF. To make the model more realistic, the averaged
315 synaptic counts of four control rhesus monkeys (seven ears) and nine frequencies
316 (Valero et al., 2017) were mapped to corresponding fractional distances of the
317 human cochlea using the monkey place-frequency map (Greenwood, 1990). frac-
318 tional distances from the base of cochlea, d_i , were calculated according to the
319 measured frequency points (f_{RM_i}):

$$f_{RM_i} [\text{in Hz}] = 360(10^{2.1(1-d_i)} - 0.85), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 9 \quad (6)$$

320

321 The obtained d_i s were substituted into the analogous Greenwood map equation

322 for humans, yielding the corresponding frequency points (f_{H_i}):

$$f_{H_i}[\text{in Hz}] = 165.4(10^{2.1(1-d_i)} - 0.88), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, 9 \quad (7)$$

323 To calibrate the model with the applied AN pattern, a 70 dB-nHL click-train con-
324 taining both stimulus polarities was presented at a rate of 11 Hz. To perform
325 this calibration, simulated ABR wave amplitudes were matched to the experi-
326 mental data on the basis of 55 averages. Specifically, the $M_1 = 4.6729 \times 10^{-14}$,
327 $M_3 = 5.6885 \times 10^{-14}$ and $M_5 = 14.641 \times 10^{-14}$ parameters were adjusted on the
328 basis of average NH ABR wave-I, III and V reference data from Picton (2010), i.e.
329 $w_I = 0.15\mu V_p$, $w_{III} = 0.17\mu V_p$ and $w_V = 0.61\mu V_{pp}$.

330 Using the synapse counts from rhesus monkey and the mapped frequency points
331 for the human cochlea (f_{H_i}), a “smoothing spline” curve was fit to estimate the
332 number of synapses across all frequency channels in the model. Finally, to simulate
333 different AN fiber types, i.e. high spontaneous-rate (HSR), medium spontaneous-
334 rate (MSR) and LSR fibers, and their properties, the obtained population dis-
335 tribution was multiplied by the corresponding AN type proportion factor C, i.e.
336 $C_{HSR} = 0.60$, $C_{MSR} = 0.25$ and $C_{LSR} = 0.15$ (Liberman, 1978, cat data), before
337 responses were summed at each simulated CF and fed to the CN model. The sim-
338 ulated frequency-specific AN fibers distribution is shown on the top-right column
339 of Fig. 4.

340 5.2. Stimuli

341 The model stimuli were matched to the experimental conditions and had a
342 duration of 600 and 400 ms for the first and second experiment, respectively.
343 Twenty stimulus repetitions with different white noise iterations were applied to
344 the model and simulations were averaged before the EFR_{PeN} was calculated using
345 the same procedure as in Eq. 4. The amplitudes of the model stimuli were set based

346 on the broadest condition, i.e. 0.25 to 22 kHz for the first experiment and 0.3 to
347 16 kHz for the second experiment to yield an input of 70 dB SPL. The narrower
348 band stimuli were calibrated relative to the broadest condition, such that they had
349 the same spectral level as the broadband condition but with a different SPL.

350 *5.3. Simulating sensorineural hearing loss*

351 The simulated CS profiles and their corresponding AN fiber types are shown
352 in Fig. 4. Different degrees of CS were modelled by manipulating the number
353 and types of AN fibers. The table in Fig. 4 shows the simulated synaptopathy
354 profiles. OHC damage was simulated by changing the CF-dependent mechanical
355 gain of the cochlea by moving poles of the BM admittance function to yield a filter
356 gain reduction corresponding to a desired dB-HL-loss, which also yielded wider
357 cochlear filters. The inset in Fig. 4 shows the simulated cochlear gain loss profiles.
358 Procedures are further detailed in Verhulst et al. (2016, 2018a).

359

360 **6. Results**

361 *6.1. EFR and dependence on stimulus frequency*

362 Figure 5 shows individual and group-mean EFR_{PtN} magnitudes to different
363 frequency bandwidths in the first (panel a) and second (panel b) experiments.
364 Despite within-group individual variability, experimental group-means revealed
365 approximately constant EFR_{PtN} magnitudes to stimuli with frequencies below
366 2 kHz and reduced magnitudes to frequencies above 2 kHz and 2.8 kHz in the
367 first and second experiment, respectively. A paired-sample t-test with Bonferroni
368 correction was applied to compare EFR_{PtN} magnitudes to stimuli with different
369 frequency bandwidths in each group. In the first experiment, a single significant
370 difference was observed between the $\text{EFR}_{[2-22]}$ and $\text{EFR}_{[4-22]}$ conditions in NH

371 group ($t(11)=7.02$, $p<0.0000$; specified by # in Fig. 5a), which disappeared for
372 the NHSR group ($t(8)=3.13$, $p=0.014$). In the second experiment, a paired-sample
373 t-test with Bonferroni correction gave a significant difference between $EFR_{[2.8-16]}$
374 and $EFR_{[5.6-16]}$ in yNH ($t(12)=7.86$, $p<0.0000$; specified by + in Fig. 5b) and
375 oNH groups ($t(12)=6.21$, $p<0.0000$; specified by ++ in Fig. 5b), but not in the
376 oHI group ($t(9)=2.03$, $p=0.072$). Simulated NH-EFRs are shown in hexagons in
377 Fig. 5 and corroborate experimental findings by showing a minor contribution of
378 stimulus frequencies below 2 kHz on the EFR generation.

379 *6.2. Derived-Band Envelope Following Responses (DBEFRs)*

380 $DBEFR_{PtN}$ magnitudes calculated using Eq. 5 are shown in Fig. 6 for the first
381 (panel a) and second (panel b) experiment. A paired-sample t-test with Bonferroni
382 correction comparing the $DBEFR_{PtN}$ magnitudes in each group revealed only a
383 significant difference between the [1-2] and [2-4] kHz condition in the NH group
384 ($t(11)=-3.99$, $p=0.002$; specified by # in Fig. 6a). In the second experiment,
385 paired-sample t-test showed significant difference between [0.3-0.7] and [2.8-5.6]-
386 kHz conditions only in yNH group ($t(12)=-7.00$, $p<0.000$; specified by + in Fig.
387 6b). In support of our experimental findings, simulated NH-DBEFR magnitudes
388 in both experiments (shown by hexagons in Fig. 6a and b) were equal for derived-
389 bands below 2-kHz and increased for $DBEFR_{[2-4]}$ (in the first experiment) and
390 $DBEFR_{[2.8-5.6]}$ (in the second experiment). In line with EFR_{PtN} findings in Sec-
391 tion 6.1, experimental and simulated $DBEFR_{PtN}$ magnitudes in both experiments
392 showed an increased contribution of the [2-6] kHz derived frequency band to the
393 EFR generation.

394 *6.3. Possible origins of individual EFR differences*

395 Previous studies have shown a dependency of the scalp-recorded AEP magni-
396 tude to head size, sex and age (Trune et al., 1988; Mitchell et al., 1989; Vasilkov

397 and Verhulst, 2019, preprint). Hence, the spread of data-points within differ-
398 ent recorded test-groups and spectral bandwidths could be explained by subject-
399 specific factors unrelated to hearing or hearing-related factors associated with the
400 main factors for grouping: (i) self-reported hearing difficulties in noisy environ-
401 ments in the first experiment, (ii) age and (iii) elevated hearing thresholds in the
402 second experiment.

403 Pooling together the NH and NHSR EFR_{PtN} magnitudes, a regression analysis
404 was conducted to investigate the effect of age, 4 kHz threshold, head size and
405 DPTH_{3000} on the $\text{EFR}_{[2-22]}$ (Fig. 7, left column) and $\text{DBEFR}_{[2-4]}$ magnitude
406 (Fig. 8, left column). None of the regressions showed a relation between tested
407 variables, suggesting that other factors than those reported were responsible for
408 the individual variability among listeners. The regression analysis on EFR_{PtN} and
409 $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ magnitudes combined from all experimental groups in the second ex-
410 periment (Fig. 7 and 8, right column) showed a meaningful correlation of age,
411 threshold, head size and DPTH_{4000} with the $\text{EFR}_{[2.8-16]}$ magnitude. However, ex-
412 tracting the $\text{DBEFR}_{[2.8-5.6]}$, reduced the correlation with age and 4-kHz threshold
413 and suppressed any meaningful correlation with head-size and DPTH_{4000} . More-
414 over, excluding the oHI group from the correlation analysis, led to a reduced and
415 insignificant correlation coefficient ($R=-0.382$, $p=0.083$) between 4-kHz threshold
416 and $\text{DBEFR}_{[2.8-5.6]}$. These results suggest that the proposed DBEFR metric is not
417 affected by head size. Moreover, individual variabilities between the yNH and oNH
418 groups in the second experiment might be related to degraded temporal envelope
419 coding as a consequence of CS (Bharadwaj et al., 2015), given the insignificant
420 correlations of DBEFRs with the 4-kHz threshold, DPTH_{4000} and head size.

421 *6.4. EFR_{PtN} and DBEFR_{PtN} magnitude variability across tested groups*

422 To investigate the separability of the recruited groups by means of their DBEFR
423 magnitudes, we analysed the group-mean differences in each experiment. In the
424 first experiment, an independent two-sample t-test comparison between the means
425 of stimulated frequency bandwidths in the NH and NHSR group (Fig. 5a), showed a
426 significant difference only between the [2-22] and [4-22]-kHz conditions (EFR_[2-22]:
427 $t(19)=3.36$, $p=0.003$ and EFR_[4-22]: $t(19)=2.76$, $p=0.012$). However, significant
428 mean-differences disappeared between similar conditions in the NH and NHSR
429 groups after extracting DBEFR magnitudes in Fig. 6a (DBEFR_[2-4]: $t(19)=0.90$,
430 $p=0.338$). The insignificant difference across groups and insignificant correlation
431 coefficients of DBEFR_[2-4] with subject-specific factors observed in Fig. 8, might
432 partly be explained by the different amounts of experienced lifetime noise exposure
433 reported in the questionnaires and might point to various degrees of noise-induced
434 CS. Calculated noise scores in Fig. 9 revealed an insignificant correlation with
435 DBEFR_[2-4] magnitudes ($R=0.13$, $p=0.089$). However, certain cases appeared
436 to be inconsistent with our noise-induced synaptopathy hypothesis, i.e., (i) high
437 noise scores in the NH group, e.g. subject No. 12 and (ii) low noise scores in the
438 NHSR group, e.g. subject No. 1. We suggest that the insignificant group-mean
439 differences can be explained by (i) subject-dependent unreliable discriminating fac-
440 tor between NH and NHSR group (Coughlin, 1990), (ii) variability in answering
441 lifetime noise-exposure dose in questionnaires (Prendergast et al., 2017; Bramhall
442 et al., 2017), (iii) an insufficient number of samples and (iv) a limited sensitivity
443 of the DBEFR_{PtN} metric to noise-induced CS.

444 In the second experiment, an independent two-sample t-test was applied to
445 investigate the effect of age between the yNH and oNH groups, and elevated high-
446 frequency thresholds between the oNH and oHI groups. This comparison showed
447 a significant effect of age on all frequency bandwidths and a significant effect of

448 hearing threshold on all frequency bands except for the [5.6-16] kHz band ($t(21)$
449 $= -1.81$, $p = 0.084$). The same comparison for the DBEFR magnitudes revealed
450 a significant effect of age and hearing threshold only in the [2.8-5.6]-kHz derived
451 band condition ($t(24) = 3.13$, $p=0.004$ and $t(21) = -4.60$, $p = 0.002$, respectively),
452 consistent with the correlation presented in Fig. 8. Detailed t and p values of
453 independent two-sample t-tests, evaluating the effect of age and hearing thresholds
454 on EFR and DBEFR magnitudes, are listed in Table. 1.

455 Our group-mean results combined with the correlation analysis in Section 6.3
456 suggests that the DBEFR metric removes inter-subject variability unrelated to
457 hearing between yNH and oNH groups, but leaves individual magnitude differences
458 within a group meaningful, given the often non-overlapping standard deviations.
459 Consequently, the significant group-mean difference between yNH and oNH might
460 reflect individual degrees of sensorineural hearing loss. To investigate the diagnos-
461 tic sensitivity, it is of course necessary to understand the respective role of OHC
462 deficits and CS on DBEFR magnitudes. Given that oHI listeners may suffer from
463 both OHC deficits and CS, it is important to study the impact of OHC-damage
464 and CS, both independently and concomitantly.

465 *6.5. The EFR relationship to different aspects of sensory hearing-loss*

466 Since OHC-damage and CS might both affect the EFR magnitude (Garrett
467 and Verhulst, 2019; Vasilkov and Verhulst, 2019, preprint), we employed a compu-
468 tational model of the auditory periphery to simulate how different degrees of CS
469 affected the EFR_{PtN} magnitude, both in presence and absence of high-frequency
470 sloping OHC-loss above 1 kHz (simulated high-frequency sloping audiograms in
471 Fig. 4). The most sensitive regions of the cochlea responding to a 120-Hz mod-
472 ulated broadband noise were identified to lie between the CFs of 2 and 6 kHz
473 (Keshishzadeh et al., 2019). As a result, we only considered two EFR condi-

474 tions of each experiment, namely $\text{EFR}_{[2-22]}$ and $\text{EFR}_{[4-22]}$ in the first experiment
475 (Fig. 10a) and $\text{EFR}_{[2.8-16]}$ and $\text{EFR}_{[5.6-16]}$ in the second experiment (Fig. 10b).
476 Model simulations showed that CS, when no other hearing deficits co-occur, re-
477 duces the EFR and DBEFR magnitudes. Applying sloping high-frequency OHC-
478 damage increased the DBEFR magnitudes in both experiments (Fig. 10c and d).
479 According to the simulations, the NH DBEFR magnitude reduced by 46% as a
480 consequence of removing 47% of the AN fibers (i.e., the 10-0-0 CS profile defined
481 in Fig. 4), while the Slope20 OHC-damage (defined in Fig. 4) increased the NH
482 DBEFR magnitude by 27%. Hence, the effect of OHC-damage on the DBEFR
483 magnitude is smaller than that of CS alone, however it is not negligible. There-
484 fore, the experimental range of individual EFR and DBEFR magnitudes can be
485 explained by different degrees of variation simulated by CS and OHC-damage.

486 Our simulations predicted the experimental observed absolute range of DBEFR
487 magnitudes and explained the experimental differences between yNH and oNH
488 groups on the basis of age-induced CS, not OHC-damage induced differences. Fur-
489 thermore, the simulations suggest that oNH and oHI listeners might both suffer
490 from CS. Results are less clear for the NHR group where there is a strong overlap
491 with the NH group. However, the noise scores from the questionnaires in Fig. 9,
492 could ascribe some of the spread in DBEFR magnitudes within the NH and NHR
493 groups to noise-induced CS, and to a lesser degree to OHC-damage given all had
494 normal hearing thresholds.

495 It is worthwhile to note that EFR magnitudes in both experiments (Fig. 10a
496 and b), decreased as a result of CS alone and increased by applying high-frequency
497 OHC-damage with a severity of less than 20 dB-HL at 8 kHz. However, higher
498 degrees of OHC-damage reduced the EFR magnitudes. We explain this non-
499 monotonic behaviour on the basis of the AN fiber discharge rate-level curve,
500 where increased simulated EFR_{PtN} magnitudes (Fig. 10 c and d) and amplitude-

501 modulated (AM) responses (Fig. 11b) to supra-threshold stimuli (70 dB-SPL)
502 caused by OHC-damage, might stem from the extended dynamic range of the AN
503 fibers for less effective AN-driving levels (Bharadwaj et al., 2014, their Fig. 3c).
504 Given that experimental and simulated stimuli were calibrated to have equal spec-
505 tral magnitudes for all stimulus bandwidths, the narrowest bandwidth stimulus
506 was presented at a lower overall sound level than the 70 dB-SPL broadband stim-
507 ulus. Thus, applying more severe OHC-loss, lowered the AN discharge rate and
508 envelope synchrony strength (Verhulst et al., 2018a, Fig. 5) and decreased the
509 EFR magnitudes (Verhulst et al., 2018a, their Fig. 7). However, DBEFR magni-
510 tudes increased monotonically for all simulated degrees of OHC damage (Fig. 10c
511 and d).

512 7. Discussion

513 7.1. Tonotopic sensitivity of the EFR generators

514 Despite the individual variability within groups, experimental group-mean
515 EFR_{PtN} magnitudes to broadband stimuli with different bandwidths (Fig. 5a),
516 were equal at frequencies below 4 kHz and reduced in response to [4-22] kHz
517 condition. In the second experiment (Fig. 5b), the EFRs remained equal at fre-
518 quencies below 5.6 kHz and degraded when the [5.6-16] kHz band was added.
519 Consequently, equal $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ magnitudes were obtained for frequencies below
520 2 kHz. Individual variability was best observed for the $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ extracted from
521 the [2-4] kHz (first experiment, Fig. 6a) and [2.8-5.6] kHz (second experiment,
522 Fig. 6b) frequency bands. Simulated EFRs to the experimental stimuli shown
523 with hexagons in Fig. 5 and 6, confirmed observed experimental EFR_{PtN} and
524 $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ frequency-dependent behaviour. In addition, the model can be used
525 to study which CF regions along the cochlea contributed strongly to the population

526 EFR response. To this end, we calculated the AM (Fig. 11a) and derived-band
 527 AM (DBAM) responses at each CF (Fig. 11b) as follows:

$$AM_{AN}(N_{CF}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^2 [2 |\text{FFT}(AN_{N_{CF}})|]_{f_i}, \quad (8)$$

$$N_{CF} = 1, 2, \dots, 401, f_i = 120 \times (i + 1)$$

$$DBAM_{AN} = |AM_{AN}(\text{wide}) - AM_{AN}(\text{narrow})| \quad (9)$$

528 $AN_{N_{CF}}$ is the AN-response at N_{CF} channel and $n = n_1$ as was defined in Eq. 1.
 529 These simulations corroborate the experimentally-observed minor contribution of
 530 low-frequency CF channels to the EFR generation.

531 In a previous modelling study (Keshishzadeh et al., 2019), we investigated
 532 the tonotopic sensitivity of EFR_{PtN} to broadband stimuli and ascribed the poor
 533 low-frequency AM coding to a combination of the chosen modulation frequency
 534 (120 Hz) and the narrower bandwidth of apical cochlear filters compared to the
 535 higher CF filters (Moore and Glasberg, 1983). Model simulations in response to
 536 the spectrally broadest condition, i.e. [0.25-22] kHz, modulated with a range of
 537 lower modulation frequencies than 120 Hz, showed that the saturation proper-
 538 ties of AN fibers limited the modulation response at all modulation frequencies
 539 at higher CFs despite an enhanced modulated response at the BM. This resulted
 540 in a degraded response at CFs above 4 kHz and shifted the frequency sensitivity
 541 of AM coding to the lower CFs at low modulation frequencies. Since the brain
 542 response to modulation frequencies below 70 Hz may contain cortical as well as
 543 brainstem contribution (Purcell et al., 2004; Picton, 2010, Chapter 10), employing
 544 low modulation frequencies might render EFR-based CS diagnosis insensitive, even
 545 though an improved frequency-sensitivity can be obtained from the apical regions
 546 using these lower modulation frequencies. Therefore, the employed experimen-

547 tal modulation frequency, i.e. 120-Hz in combination with a broadband carrier,
548 might be able to establish a frequency-specific CS diagnosis at frequencies above
549 2 kHz. In this context, the proposed DBEFR method showed a notable contribu-
550 tion of the [2-4] kHz CF region to the EFR generation by showing a significantly
551 stronger $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ magnitude compared to lower derived-band conditions in the
552 NH group.

553 *7.2. Diagnostic Applications*

554 The measured DBEFR magnitudes are individually separable and above the
555 noise-floor even for HI listeners, whose group-mean was significantly above the
556 noise-floor. In addition, the DBEFR offers a frequency-specific metric to assess
557 supra-threshold temporal coding of the population of AN fibers and brainstem
558 neurons in the [2-6] kHz region. Despite these promising results, the diagnostic
559 sensitivity of DBEFRs also has limitations. The proposed DBEFR magnitude is
560 sensitive to CS alone, when no other coexisting hearing deficits occur and is hence
561 applicable for use in ageing listeners with normal audiograms and those with self-
562 reported hearing difficulties or prone to noise exposure. However, DBEFRs are
563 also affected by OHC damage (Fig. 10). The metric hence needs to be comple-
564 mented with another supra-threshold metric sensitive to OHC damage within the
565 tonotopic range of interest to allow a separation of the CS and OHC aspect of
566 sensorineural hearing damage from the recorded DBEFRs from listeners with im-
567 paired audiograms.

568 Lastly, the employed high modulation frequency, i.e. 120 Hz, suppresses corti-
569 cal contributions to the EFR_{PtN} magnitudes, but also degrades AM-coding from
570 lower CFs and thereby limits the tonotopic sensitivity of the EFR_{PtN} to frequen-
571 cies above 2 kHz. Consequently, apical-end supra-threshold hearing deficits would
572 not be reflected in the proposed $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ metric even for stimuli which contain

573 frequencies below 2 kHz. These results are consistent with the source generators of
574 derived-band ABRs (DBABR), which reduce in amplitude for bands below 2 kHz
575 (Don and Eggermont, 1978). This predominant basal origin of the ABR also con-
576 fines the potential of ABR/DBABR-based CS diagnosis to basal cochlear regions
577 (e.g. wave-I amplitude).

578 **8. Conclusion**

579 We proposed the use of a relative $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ metric to render the EFR_{PtN}
580 frequency-specific and rule out subject-specific factors unrelated to hearing to ap-
581 ply it in the study of identifying the origins of sensorineural hearing deficits and
582 clarifying their role in supra-threshold temporal envelope encoding. $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$
583 magnitudes from two experiments were analysed and compared to model sim-
584 ulations to conclude that the frequency-sensitivity of $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ magnitudes to
585 broadband stimuli is limited to the [2-6] kHz bandwidth. Secondly, we showed that
586 the DBEFR metric eliminates inter-subject variability caused by hearing-unrelated
587 sources. Model simulations (Fig. 10) explained the significant difference between
588 yNH and oNH listeners on the basis of CS, which could result from age-induced
589 CS as identified from human post-mortem studies (Makary et al., 2011; Viana
590 et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2019). Supported by model predictions (Fig. 10d), the
591 significant difference between age-matched oNH and oHI groups was explained by
592 OHC-damage and coexisting CS as a consequence of ageing. Accordingly, profound
593 OHC damage may confound DBEFR-based clinical applications of CS diagnosis.
594 Despite this limitation in the differential diagnosis of CS and OHC deficits on
595 the basis of the DBEFR magnitude, the proposed metric can be used to diagnose
596 CS in a frequency-specific manner in listeners with thresholds below 20 dB-HL.
597 Moreover, it provides an objective marker of supra-threshold temporal envelope
598 coding, which can be used to study its role in sound perception studies. Lastly,

599 our results clearly demonstrate that older listeners with or without impaired au-
600 diograms suffer from degraded temporal envelope coding at frequencies above 2
601 kHz.

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Table 1: The results of a two-tailed t test show the effect of age and hearing threshold on EFR and DBEFR magnitudes in the second experiment.

Metric	Frequency Bandwidth	Age Effect	Threshold Effect
	[kHz]	yNH vs. oNH	oNH vs. oHI
EFR	[0.3-16]	t(24)=5.812 p=0.000	t(21)=-3.020 p=0.006
	[0.7-16]	t(24)=6.632 p=0.000	t(21)=-2.175 p=0.041
	[2.8-16]	t(24)=5.836 p=0.000	t(21)=-4.498 p=0.000
	[5.6-16]	t(24)=4.734 p=0.000	t(21)=-1.811 p=0.084
DBEFR	[0.3-0.7]	t(24)=-2.09 p=0.050	t(21)=-0.86 p=0.40
	[2.8-5.6]	t(24)=3.13 p=0.004	t(21)=-4.60 p=0.002

Figure 1. Measured audiograms in the first (left) and second (right) experiment. Markers indicate the audiometric threshold at 4 kHz. The dashed line is the averaged audiometric threshold at each group and the yellow shading the standard deviation.

Figure 2. Spectra of the 120-Hz modulated stimuli and derived bands. (a) Designed stimulus spectra in different frequency bands and specified cut-off frequencies of the bandpass filter. (b) Derived bands from the EFRs recorded to the stimuli shown in (a) obtained by spectral subtraction.

Figure 3. Magnitude spectrum of the $EFR_{\text{raw}}(f)$ (in blue), $\text{Noisefloor}(f)$ (in red) and $EFR_{\text{Spec}}(f)$ (in black) calculated for subject No. 8 from the first experiment. EFR spectra were evoked by the stimulus with the broadest bandwidth, i.e. [0.25-22] kHz. Peaks at the stimulus modulation frequency, and two harmonics (i.e. $f_0 = 120\text{Hz}$, $f_1 = 240\text{Hz}$ and $f_2 = 360\text{Hz}$) are clearly visible above the noise-floor.

Figure 4. Modeling approach. The block-diagram shows different levels of the auditory pathway modelled in the employed biophysical model of the hearing periphery (Verhulst et al., 2018a). The top-right graph indicates the simulated distribution of different types of AN fibers across CF. The table shows simulated CS profiles and the graph on the bottom right depicts sim-

ulated different degrees of cochlear gain loss. The corresponding simulated thresholds at 8 kHz are indicated by the legend.

Figure 5. EFR_{PtN} magnitudes to 120-Hz modulated stimuli with different white noise carrier bandwidths in the (a) first and (b) second experiment. Individual data-points are depicted with open symbols and standard deviations were obtained using a bootstrapping procedure (Zhu et al., 2013). Filled symbols reflect the group-means and their corresponding standard deviations. Simulated EFRs from a NH model were added in filled hexagons. Significant effects of considered frequency-band on EFR_{PtN} magnitudes are specified by: (#) in the NH-group (first experiment), (+) in the yNH-group and (++) in the oNH-group (second experiment). To enhance the visualization of differences, panel (a) was plotted on narrower y-axis range, therefore the real values of lowered EFR_{PtN} magnitudes were specified next to the corresponding data-points.

Figure 6. $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ magnitudes derived using Eq. 5 for 120 Hz modulated stimuli with different white-noise-carrier bandwidths in the (a) first and (b) second experiment. $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ for each frequency band was obtained from a wider and narrower width stimulus. Standard deviations were calculated using a bootstrapping procedure and stemmed from averaged responses from 20 stimulus iterations in the model simulations. Group means and standard deviations are depicted using filled symbols. Significant effects of considered frequency-band on NH-group in the first experiment and yNH-group in the second experiment are specified by (#) and (+), respectively. To enhance the visualization of differences, figures were plotted on narrower y-axis range,

therefore the real values of lowered $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ magnitudes were specified next to the corresponding data-points.

Figure 7. Correlation analysis of $\text{EFR}_{[2-22]}$ ($\text{EFR}_{[2.8-16]}$) with age, audiometric threshold at 4 kHz, head-size and DPTH_{3000} (DPTH_{4000}) in the first (left) and second (right) experiments. Correlation between EFR magnitudes and all factors but age were reported using the Pearson's correlation coefficient. The Spearman's correlation coefficient was calculated to study the effect of age in the second experiment.

Figure 8. Correlation analysis of $\text{DBEFR}_{[2-4]}$ ($\text{DBEFR}_{[2.8-5.6]}$) with age, audiometric threshold at 4 kHz, head-size and DPTH_{3000} (DPTH_{4000}) in the first (left) and second (right) experiments. Correlation between DBEFR magnitudes and all factors but age were reported using the Pearson's correlation coefficient. The Spearman's correlation coefficient was calculated to study the effect of age in the second experiment.

Figure 9. Bar-plots of noise scores acquired from questionnaires of NH and NHSR groups, classified in three categories, i.e. experience noise as a consequence of (i) playing a musical instrument in a band, (ii) attending festivals or concerts and (iii) using noisy tools. Results are shown normalised, where the score of 1 corresponds to 30600, 18480 and 26000 hours of accumulated noise dose on the considered categories, respectively.

Figure 10. Experimental EFR_{PtN} and $\text{DBEFR}_{\text{PtN}}$ magnitudes (colored open symbols): (a) EFR_{PtN} to [2-22] and [4-22] kHz, (b) EFR_{PtN} to [2.8-16] and

[5.6-16] kHz and (c) DBEFR_{PtN} at [2-4] kHz and (d) DBEFR_{PtN} at [2.8-5.6] kHz. Simulated EFR_{PtN} (a,b) and DBEFR_{PtN} (c,d) magnitudes are shown in each panel using filled hexagons and degrees of CS as indicated on the X axis and CF-dependent patterns of OHC damage as given by the legend.

Figure 11. Modulated responses calculated at each CF using Eq. 8 and 9 to different experimental conditions for normal listeners and different sensorineural hearing losses at the AN processing level of the model, (a) broadband and (b) derived-band. In both panels, dotted lines show AM-responses to sloping 10 dB-HL OHC-loss at 8 kHz and lighter colors indicate AM responses to certain degree of CS.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

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Figure 11